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“Book review of “Intercultural Communication
and Identity” by Ron Darvin and Tongle Sun 2024,
68pp.”

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Abstract

Book review of “*Intercultural Communication and Identity*” by Ron Darvin and Tongle Sun, Cambridge 2024.

Keywords

Intercultural communication; identity; poststructuralist; globalization; online space

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Introduction

In (post) modern society, identity no longer serves as the centre of the individual, but possesses a high degree of multiplicity, variability and flexibility (Simon, 2004). This increasingly pluralistic and fluid mode of communication has a profound impact on people's identities.

In the context of intercultural communication, social identity is a topic that has been studied by scholars (such as Kõiv, 2024; Zhang, 2024) for many years. More and more scholars have criticized social identity or cultural identity under the existing perspective of Western cross-cultural research. Since the 1980s, biculturalism has been highly regarded in cross-cultural studies (Liu, 2015). Existing studies have overemphasized the binary opposition, such as the opposition between the native culture and the host culture. The increasing complexity of global migration has also challenged the binary opposition. Moreover, research tends to treat cultural differences as problems rather than as resources for communication and understanding, which limits understanding of the complexities of identity. In (post) modern society, identity no longer serves as the centre of the individual, but possesses a high degree of multiplicity, variability and flexibility (Simon, 2004). This increasingly pluralistic and fluid mode of communication has a profound impact on people's identities. Against this background, this book discusses the importance of identity studies in critical intercultural communication in the context of globalization, giving due consideration to identity in a multicultural context. It also analyzes how identity is constructed and mediated through discourse from social psychology, poststructuralist, critical perspectives and analyzes the understanding of identity from different theoretical perspectives. In the Introduction section, the importance of identity as a fundamental concept in the field of language and intercultural communication is emphasized. Identity is seen as subjectivity "is constructed through language" (p. 1), which is expressed and negotiated by individuals through linguistic and symbolic resources in different intercultural contexts. In addition, the introduction also mentions the impact of globalization on identity and how identity studies can help understand how individuals are positioned and expressed in different cultural exchanges.

The second chapter entitled *Theorizing Identity* discusses identity theory from social psychology, poststructuralist and critical perspectives, indicating the importance of identity as a fundamental concept in the field of language and intercultural communication. These theoretical perspectives provide an important framework for understanding the role of identity in intercultural communication.

The following three chapters probe into the specific manifestation and influencing factors of identity in intercultural communication. In the third chapter, the author pointed out that "identity is fluid, as it is constructed, mediated, and negotiated in different ways" (p. 10). The author stated how digital world serves as a medium that enables individuals to maintain their identity and membership in a specific community, thereby interacting and communicating with others in the online world. Chapter Four holds that categorizing identity is an important part of cultural identity. Cultural identity involves the use and identification of race, ethnicity, nationality and social class. In intercultural interactions, individuals can position themselves through a process of identification and they are

positioned by others through a process of ascription. Race and ethnicity are often conflated, but race is an “ideological construct” (p. 18) rather than a biological classification system. The case of a Colombian man shows how people are marked in intercultural experiences by class orientation. The author then zooms in onto identity construction in different contexts, which combines mentioned theories with actual sociocultural contexts. In the context of language learning and teaching, learners will face marginality and unequal power relations, which will affect their identity negotiation and construction, so they will change different identities in different situations. Immigrant families have “the differences in multilingual practices and transnational identity construction” (p. 27), and language ideologies in society and unequal power relations will affect the intercultural communication of them. For sojourners, individual differences and external factors can experience varying degrees of intercultural engagement and identity expansion, which is mediated by the sojourners’ linguistic background, gender, race, and social class.

After the theories and concepts of identity, the following chapter delves deeper into the application of different research methods in identity research, which includes ethnography, case study, narrative inquiry, conversation analysis, critical discourse analysis and digital ethnography. Through these methods, identity researchers can cast a light on the complexity and contradictions of individuals and find generalizable connections. The final chapter concludes the book by emphasizing the importance of identity studies in critical intercultural communication in a globalized world. Future research directions are proposed, including critical reflection on existing theories and methods, as well as exploration of emerging research areas.

The book combines social psychology, poststructuralist, critical theory, sociology, anthropology, and applied linguistics to provide a rich theoretical foundation for understanding intercultural communication and identity by integrating these interdisciplinary perspectives. This book provides readers with a comprehensive and in-depth analytical framework to understand how identity is constructed, manifested and negotiated in intercultural interactions in the context of globalization and digitization. Integrating different disciplines helps integrate the theory and practice of identity, including language learning, migration, study abroad, multicultural work environments, and online interaction.

The case studies in this book combine multiple perspectives such as social psychology, poststructuralist and critical theory. They not only have theoretical value, but also are highly practical and applicable, which can help readers better understand the complexity in cross-cultural communication and improve their cross-cultural communication skills. For instance, by studying the identity of language teachers and the issue of identity in cross-cultural training, the book provides specific guidance for educators, helping them design more effective teaching plans. These cases not only enrich theoretical research, but also provide specific guidance and suggestions, and have significant academic value and practical significance. Another contribution of this book is the introduction of multiple approaches to identity research, showing how theoretical frameworks can be combined with empirical research, including ethnography, case studies, narrative inquiry, conversation analysis, critical discourse analysis, and digital ethnography, providing researchers with a wealth of research tools. Therefore, it can be recommended to scholars who work or teach in related fields.

At the same time, some of the issues touched upon in the book need to be addressed further. Especially in the early stages of the study, how to avoid making preconceived assumptions about the identity of the participants? Researchers need to be more reflective in order to understand how their own identities affect their interpretation of interactions and to ensure they do not reproduce processes of othering and objectifying research subjects. It is expected that research also needs to include the lifestyles and behaviors of indigenous people, rural people and members of the Global South to integrate more diverse forms of knowledge.

The book could benefit from a wider diverse scope if it could include marginalized groups into discussion, such as the homeless and refugees. Theoretical frameworks may become incomplete by ignoring the experiences and practices of marginalized groups, limiting the depth and breadth of theories. If the research does not take into account the needs and challenges of marginalized groups, the proposed practices may not be applicable to all groups, leading to limitations in application. For example, a study by Chandra (2022) on the identity of gay men showed that the family of origin was important to identity formation, which challenges the dominant understanding that gay men's identities exist separately to them (Chandra, 2022). Therefore, paying attention to marginalized groups of different species is essential for building a comprehensive and inclusive social theoretical framework. Readers are able to gain a deeper understanding of how social structures and individual identities are formed and developed in different contexts.

In discussing online space, the book focuses on the complexity and dynamics of intercultural communication in online space. Although the identity constructed by people in online space inherits some political concepts and social structures in the era of traditional media, social media enables more extensive contact and communication between different cultures in intercultural communication. Thus, it has an impact on the shaping of personal identity. A study of TikTok shows that users need to actively search for related content; otherwise, the algorithm is hidden by default (Karizat et al., 2021). The researchers advocated for the consideration of identity and how it functions (and is believed to function) with an algorithm in all efforts to improve users' algorithmic experience. In this way, it contributes to the development of genuinely inclusive technologies with representational belonging possible for all its users.

People's identities and sense of belonging can be altered, so individual, collective, and national identities can become blurred in cyberspace. The National web is an entity that emerges and exists in flux, through the production and circulation of culturally significant content and genres that help establish its boundaries (Boichak and Kumar, 2021). Thus, if cyberspace is handled properly, citizens' sense of national identity can be significantly enhanced. Therefore, in the era of social media, it is necessary to further study and understand the connection between identity reconstruction and intercultural communication in order to better cope with the challenges brought by social media and give play to its advantages.

Overall, the book provides a comprehensive and in-depth framework for the study of intercultural identity and provides important theoretical and methodological guidance for understanding the changes of identity in the context of globalization.

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